

The breeding methods used by 31 rice breeders at 24 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian countries, 1975.

Breeding method	1st		2nd		Choice of method				Users ^a	
	no.	%	no.	%	3rd		4th		no.	%
Pedigree	21	68	3	10	3	10	2	6	29	94
Backcross	2	6	10	32	5	16	2	6	19	60
Bulk	1	3	9	29	5	16	0	0	15	48
Mutation ^b	0	0	3	10	4	13	5	16	12	39
Combination	6	19	3	10	5	16	4	13	18	58
Others	1	3	1	3	5	16	1	3	8	26
No indication	0	0	2	6	4	13	17	55	—	—

^aThe number and percentage of 31 breeders who indicated that they used each method as at least one of their breeding systems.

^bChemical, radiation, or natural.

Sixty-eight percent of the breeders (21) depended primarily on the pedigree method of breeding (see table); two breeders depended mostly on the backcross method, and one on the bulk method. Six breeders (19%) indicated that they depended primarily on a combination of breeding techniques.

Ninety-four percent of all breeders

surveyed used the pedigree system (in combination with other methods); 60% used the backcross method; and 48%, the bulk system.

Although none of the breeders depended primarily on mutation breeding (chemical, radiation, or natural) in their programs, 39% used mutation in combination with other methods.

ARC 11775 — an Assam rice cultivar that is promising for rainfed lowlands

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Kerala state grows 395,000 ha of monsoon rice. More than 80% of the area under autumn rice is sown in dry soil in mid-April during the premonsoon showers and later flooded as the southwest monsoon advances. Farmers dry sow the autumn rice so they can harvest it early and immediately transplant the winter rice, which depends on the meager and erratic northeast monsoon rains. The autumn rice crop is subjected to two major stresses: drought

during initial growth stages and weeds. A few semidwarf rices withstand some drought but they are more prone to smothering by weeds than are the local tall varieties. Farmers prefer tall, nonlodging rice with a lush canopy of leaves. But the present tall cultivars lodge, even before panicle emergence, and suffer severe yield losses.

Preliminary investigations indicated the adaptability for dry sowing of some elite International Rice Yield Nursery (IRYN) rices of intermediate stature.

Among the rices in the Assam Rice Collection, the accession ARC 11775 has been identified as drought tolerant, tall, nonlodging, and fertilizer responsive, with a high degree of blast resistance. Its seed-to-seed growth duration is 105 to 110 days vs. 130 to 135 days for the

Characteristics of ARC 11775 a promising cultivar for rainfed lowlands, and a tall local variety. Kerala, India.

Variety	Growth duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield (kg/day)	Kernel color
ARC 11775	106	2.5	26.6	White
Ptb 26 (local tall indica)	135	1.8	13.0	Red

most popular tall varieties (See table).

The yield per day of ARC 11775 is double that of the all local variety now grown. Earliness without yield loss is desirable for autumn rice so that popular winter rices can be transplanted earlier in rainfed paddies.

Suakoko 8 — a new rice variety recommended for iron-toxic swamps in Liberia

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Rice varieties with genetic tolerance to iron toxicity are considered useful in many inland valley swamps in Liberia, where symptoms of the disorder develop in most rice crops. Gissi 27, a local variety recommended for deep waterlogged swamps, is tolerant of iron toxicity. But being tall, photoperiod sensitive, and late maturing (165 – 170 days), it cannot be used for double-cropping or for high-technology rice cultivation. IR5 is recommended for inland valley swamps, but it is susceptible to iron toxicity, which reduces its yields by as much as 40%.

More than 3,000 rice varieties have been screened and tested during the past 4 years at the Central Agricultural Experiment Station, Suakoko. Emphasis has been on varietal tolerance for iron toxicity in inland swamps. The most significant result is the selection of the line 2526 (Siam 25/Malunja³), which is tolerant of iron toxicity and has been named Suakoko 8 by the Liberian Ministry of Agriculture.

In trials across the country during the past 3 years, Suakoko 8 outyielded IR5 by about 20% in iron-toxic swamps. Under nontoxic conditions, IR5 and Suakoko 8 yield similarly but farmers in various parts of Liberia prefer Suakoko 8 because it has better cooking quality and is more palatable.

Mr. A. J. Carpenter, then rice agronomist, Food and Agriculture Organization, United Nations

Development Program, introduced the 2526 strain from Malaysia in 1973. Because the line was heterogeneous, it was further selected at Suakoko for adaptability and uniformity. The released population of Suakoko 8 is fairly uniform, photoperiod insensitive, and matures in about 140 days. It has good seedling vigor; good tillering ability; semicompact plant type; intermediate culms of intermediate diameter;

intermediate senescence; well-exserted, long, and heavy panicles; glabrous, pale green, and intermediate leaves; and erect flag leaves. Its grains are long, slender, and translucent. It suffers less damage than IR5 from the important diseases such as blast, sheath rot, sheath blight, leaf scald, and brown spot, as well as caseworm. Because it is photoperiod insensitive, Suakoko 8 is also superior to Gissi 27. Its plant type is well suited to

Liberian peasant farm conditions of imperfect water control, moderate fertilization, and manual harvesting.

During the 1977 wet season, Suakoko 8 seed were distributed for minikit and production kit trials. Seed is expected to reach a large number of farmers for planting in the 1978 wet season. **W**

India's national gene bank in international cooperation

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The national rice germ plasm bank of India is maintained at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack. The collection started with about 2,000 varieties obtained from the paddy breeding station, Coimbatore, in 1946–47. It gradually increased as varieties were obtained from different

states and abroad by request and exchange. About 10,000 additional varieties were added from systematic surveys from Jeypore tract of Orissa (1955–59); Manipur state (1965–70); northeastern India (Assam Rice Collection, 1968–71); and new collections, mostly from upland and rainfed tracts of nine states (1976–77). The national gene bank at present consists of 14,905 varieties (Table 1).

Supplying traditional cultivars to scientists and institutions inside India and abroad is an important activity of

the national center. About 5,000 varieties have been sent to scientists and institutions in 24 countries during the last decade. A few countries and institutions that have received large numbers of accessions, particularly from 1974 to 1977, are shown in Table 2. **W**

Newest rice varieties in 10 Asian nations

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To determine the types of new rice varieties going out to farmers in Asia, IRRI surveyed rice breeders at 29 research centers in 10 countries on the varieties that had been released by their stations during the previous 5 years. The research project, initiated in 1975, was partially funded by a research grant from the Rockefeller Foundation.

Twenty-seven of the experiment stations had released 165 new varieties (two stations had not released any varieties during the time period). For all stations surveyed, the average number of released varieties was 5.7, or a little more than one new variety per year. For only the stations that had released varieties during the 5-year period, the average was 6.1 varieties/station.

Next, each breeder was asked how many of the new varieties had been bred locally (within his country) and how many had come from IRRI. Breeders were also asked to name the parents of locally bred varieties.

Seventy-eight percent of the 165 varieties had been bred in the countries where they were released; 22% were developed at IRRI (see figure).

Table 1. Present status of national gene bank at Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

Source	Varieties (no.)			Total
	Early maturity	Medium maturity	Late maturity	
World collection (AC no.)	1,386	1,254	924	3,564
Jeypore Botanical Survey (JBS no.)	241	1,006	321	1,568
Manipur collection (MNP no.)	40	495	224	759
Assam Rice Collection (ARC no.)	447	4,874	207	5,528
Miscellaneous collection	550	1,155	350	2,055
New collection from states (NCS no., duration not yet classified)	—	—	—	1,431
Total	2,664	8,784	2,026	14,905

Table 2. Countries and institutions that have received major supplies of seed from the national gene bank, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

Country	Varieties supplied (no.)				Total
	1974	1975	1976	1977	
IRRI (Philippines)	22	24	65	2,893	3,004
USSR	22	32	41	253 ^a	348
West Africa	28	34	69	8	139
Vietnam	—	41	9	—	50
USA	—	—	1	33	34
Liberia	—	35	—	—	35
Total	72	166	185	3,187	3,610

^a Includes material committed to be sent.